

From classical geometric computer vision to geometric deep learning, new challenges in autonomous driving

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Geometric computer vision describes the structure and shape of the world. Specifically, the algorithms based on multi-view geometry are widely used in the estimation of measures such as depth, volume, shape, pose, disparity, motion or optical flow and they are an essential part of Autonomous Driving (AD) systems. Visual perception for autonomous driving is highly influenced by the accuracy of these geometric applications like structure from motion, visual odometry, simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) or visual HD mapping. Deep learning has played a significant role in vision 2D, demonstrating generalize better in tasks as detection, recognition and segmentation than the classical approaches and has become a mature solution for autonomous driving. Recently, they have become state of the art method for certain tasks like flow and depth estimation just by using convolutional neural network (CNN) models without incorporating geometric structure. There are also attempts at using CNN for visual SLAM, visual odometry and calibration. Therefore, there is an emergence of deep learning based approaches for geometric vision algorithms in AD systems.

2. Aim

An evaluation and analysis of the state of the art in Geometric Deep Learning. Applicability and challenges in Autonomous Driving systems.

3. Keywords

Computer Vision; Deep Learning; Autonomous Driving, Robotic Perception

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